

Can a Software Project be Riddled with Diseases?

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Abstract—Context. In software maintenance, one of the tasks that is of interest to both researchers and practitioners is software defect prediction. Many works in this area utilize statistical, time-series, and machine learning models. However, to our knowledge, few works leverage the topology of the software architectural network for this purpose.

Aim. In this registered report, we outline our planned study to construct a model to simulate and predict the spread of software defects within the software architectural network. This model will allow us to simulate the effects of different remediation strategies, such as refactorings, to slow down the spread of the defects and enable the construction of a digital twin of a software system.

Method. We will reconstruct the architecture of big monolithic systems for many releases and leverage established software metrics such as technical debt and complexity from a major dataset to define the defects whose spread we aim to predict. We will train the Susceptible-Infected-Susceptible disease spreading model and learn the optimal parameters to predict the spread of defects in software projects with minimal error.

Expected contributions. The discovery of a model of a “disease” spreading on the evolving architecture of the system will affect how we approach the assessment, maintenance, and evolution of software projects, since creating a digital twin of a software product to simulate different refactoring and development scenarios for practitioners would be possible. Conversely, a negative result would also be important, indicating that the focus and attention should be given to developing alternative theories and models of defect evolution in software.

Index Terms—software architecture, software evolution, software defects, defect prediction, disease spreading, temporal networks, sis model

I. INTRODUCTION

Software defects are phenomena that can affect the quality of the software, impede development and spread from component to component, such as high complexity, the presence of smells or bugs, or simply too large a size [1]. An effective strategy for allocating inspection and testing resources to the portions of the source code more likely to be defective is through defect prediction [2]. Defect prediction involves constructing time-series, statistical or Machine Learning (ML) models to anticipate the defect-proneness of software artifacts, primarily by leveraging information related to the source code or the development process [3]. Many works attempted to predict the appearance of defects based on previous observations with time-series analysis [1], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8] or find connections between different types of defects with statistical methods [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15]. However, we can hardly find works that have modeled how such defects can spread given the topology of the software architectural network, even though the role of dependencies on the spread

of defects and “ripple effects” of code changes has been conjectured [16], [17] and analyzed [18], [19], [20] before.

Software architecture (SA) can be modeled as a network of components connected to each other through dependency relationships [21]. Furthermore, by considering the development process and version history, we can observe the evolving architectural network for each release of the project [22]. In network science, such data structures are known as temporal networks [23], and the study of such evolving networks has received substantial attention in the last decade [24].

In particular, some phenomena could negatively affect different components in the network by traveling through the available connections. For the networks of humans transmitting diseases, correspondingly named *disease spreading* models have been applied on temporal networks to study the propagation and dynamics of these diseases [25]. Different processes have been successfully modeled as “diseases,” from epidemics of actual diseases affecting humans [26] to the sharing of news or misinformation [27].

In this work, we consider software defects as the “diseases” that propagate through the SA network. We will train a disease spreading model, namely the Susceptible-Infected-Susceptible model (SIS model, [28]), to predict the propagation of defects by minimizing the prediction error, as is standard practice in Machine Learning. Using the best obtained model, we will simulate different refactorings and predict the spread of defects in the original and refactored architectures to determine if these refactorings have a positive effect on impeding defect propagation.

The discovery of models that predict the spreading of certain software defects will enable us to assess the evolution of the software and its health, as well as guide the practitioners to appropriate maintenance measures with respect to these defects. If some defects are indeed prone to spreading over the architecture, it would highlight the urgency of their remediation as soon as they are discovered, since otherwise they might begin to affect other components. Conversely, if software defects do not appear to be spreading like diseases, it would indicate that they remain contained in the affected components, and thus, remediation strategies and prioritization can be different, for example, focusing on correct behavior of the software component through test prioritization.

This work will provide the following major contributions:

- Dataset of temporal networks of the software architecture of several projects reconstructed for many releases;
- Dataset of software components that are affected by different software defects in each release;

- Evaluation of the SIS disease spreading model for prediction of propagation of software defects and guidance to learning the best parameters;
- Simulation of different defect remediation approaches and refactorings leveraging the trained SIS-model.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In this section, we describe the key notions of defect prediction and disease spreading models.

A. Software Defect Prediction

Software defect prediction is a long-standing research area in software engineering, with extensive literature exploring how to identify fault-prone components [29]. Both product metrics (e.g., McCabe’s complexity [30], CK suite [31]) and process metrics (e.g., code churn [32], entropy [33]) have proven to be reliable predictors of defect-proneness [34], [35].

Building on these foundations, continuous defect prediction frameworks [36], anomaly-based techniques [37], [38] as well as machine and deep learning methods [3], [39] have enabled large-scale and explainable empirical analyses of software evolution. While traditional approaches estimate defects for releases, some works demonstrated the importance of commit-level characteristics such as developer experience, commit size, and code entropy [40], since large or complex commits are more likely to introduce defects.

Furthermore, Just-in-Time (JIT) prediction has been leveraged to enable commit-level granularity [40], [8]. Building on these ideas, Khanan et al. [41] proposed JITBot, an explainable JIT defect prediction chatbot enabling not only the defect proneness of software components but also explaining the factors contributing to the occurrence of a bug.

B. Temporal Networks

Most networks currently considered in Software Engineering consist of a set of nodes linked together without any temporal evolution [42], [22], [43]. Conversely, temporal networks have been proposed to analyze networks that maintain a constant set of nodes, but edges contain some kind of temporal information [44], [22]. The temporal network is usually represented as a sequence of regular networks, called snapshots, i.e., for the same set of nodes V and a sequence of timestamps $t = 1, 2, 3$, different sets of edges $E_t = \{(v_1, v_2) | v_1, v_2 \in V\}$ are defined.

C. Disease Spreading Models

For disease spreading models, we will stick to the terminology established in that field, so we will talk about a “disease” (or “infection”) that is spreading on the network composed of interacting nodes. Nodes can be “infected,” i.e., carry and be affected by the disease, and “healthy,” i.e., not carrying the disease. Diseases are usually modeled by assigning each node, i.e., a software component, to one of the states that describe its infection status at each time step and iterating through discrete time steps to observe the propagation of the infection [26]. One of the simplest yet powerful models is

Susceptible-Infected-Susceptible (SIS, [28]), which features the two respective states:

- **Susceptible (S)** - node that is not infected, but can catch the disease from an Infected node. The probability that S-node catches the disease from a connected I-node is given by the parameter β .
- **Infected (I)** - node that carries the disease and can infect others. An infected node can spontaneously become healthy at any time step with probability γ and return to the Susceptible state.

As a result of the simulation, the fraction of nodes infected at each time step, $i(t)$, known as the **infection rate**, is observed. The results are averaged over many runs of the simulation [25].

In the basic simulations of SIS model on temporal networks, the process iterates over all network snapshots in the dataset, and uses the available connections to turn S-nodes into I-nodes and spontaneously cure the I-nodes [26], [25]. At the beginning of the simulation, a set of nodes, called the **seed nodes**, is chosen uniformly at random as the original Infected nodes that are responsible for the disease [25]. In our setting, we can either use the set of Infected nodes from the ground truth of the first release as the seed nodes, or a random set of nodes of the same size.

For an **illustrative example**, consider Figure 1, which shows the SIS spreading process on a small SA temporal network. At the initial release $v1.0.0$, component B is set as the seed Infected node. Proceeding to release $v1.1.0$, B infects dependent components A and D, while C remains Susceptible, with each event determined independently with probability β . Finally, at release $v1.2.0$, component A has been refactored to two components A1 and A2, with the previously infected code fully merged in A1, thus the newly spawned component A2 is Susceptible; component B infected component C and then immediately lost the infection with probability γ , while component D infected component E and itself stayed infected. Moving on to future releases, components A1, C, D, and E would eventually lose the infection, with component F potentially infected by D and also eventually healing. Extensions of the temporal SIS model have been proposed, such as sampling I-node recovery time from a distribution rather than using a simple probability [45], [25], or using several preceding timestamps to determine the spread of disease [46]. Since, to our knowledge, this is the first work attempting to model and predict the spread of software defects within SA with such disease models, we will leverage the most basic technique described above to construct the simplest models.

III. EMPIRICAL STUDY DESIGN

Our empirical study design follows the guidelines defined by Wohlin et al. [47]. In the upcoming sections, we detail the specific research questions and goals that drive our study and the procedures we used for data collection and analysis

Fig. 1. Example of a SIS disease spreading process on software architecture.

A. Goal and Research Questions

The **goal** of our work is to **analyze** the spread of defects within software architecture **with the purpose of** building and learning defect propagation models **from the point of view** of network disease spreading **within** monolithic applications.

To achieve this goal, we formulated the following Research Questions (RQs):

RQ₁: Can SIS disease spreading model predict the spread of software defects?

- **RQ_{1.1}**: Can SIS disease spreading model predict the spread of technical debt?
- **RQ_{1.2}**: Can SIS disease spreading model predict the spread of code smells?
- **RQ_{1.3}**: Can SIS disease spreading model predict the spread of complexity?

We will measure different defects, e.g., technical debt (**RQ_{1.1}**), presence of bugs or code smells **RQ_{1.2}**, or high complexity (**RQ_{1.3}**). We will use them to define the “disease” by setting distribution-based thresholds and simulate the spread of this “disease” on the reconstructed architectural network with the SIS model to predict the propagation of defects.

As mentioned in the Section II, the SIS model is described by the probability of passing the infection and the rate of recovery. We will learn the best choice of such parameters by running the model with different values and minimizing the error between the actual infection rate and model prediction. We can measure the difference between the actual observed fraction of the infected components and the predicted infection rate with the RMSE, MAE, and MAPE metrics to find the pair of SIS model parameters that gives the smallest error. Moreover, we can learn specific values of SIS parameters from the ground truth data, and analyze if these learned values provide the best model, thus enabling a straightforward computation of the best parameters for any given defect or project.

Thus, we conjecture the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H₀₁ There is no difference in defect propagation prediction error between any two models;

H₀₂ SIS model with the parameters inferred from data does not yield the smallest error;

H₀₃ Optimal SIS model parameters for the same defect in different projects are similar;

H₁₁ There is at least one pair of SIS model parameters with a difference in defect propagation prediction error;

H₁₂ SIS model with the parameters inferred from data yields the smallest error;

H₁₃ Optimal SIS model parameters for the same defect are different in different projects.

In case we manage to build the SIS model that provides successful predictions of the software defects, we can proceed to leverage this model to analyze different remediation techniques:

RQ₂: Which remediation techniques can be simulated to alleviate the disease?

By leveraging our constructed SIS model, we can proceed to explore whether simulating remediation techniques, such as refactoring, could demonstrate a positive effect on the system’s health. For example, we could simulate a refactoring in which all hub components are removed, thus forcing an upper bound on how many connections each component can have. We could then observe how our model predicts the spread of defects on the original SA network and the network with the refactoring simulated. Thus, we are interested in refactorings and changes that do not modify the functionality of the program, but only affect the structure and composition of files and classes, so that potentially fewer dependencies between them results in slower spreading of defects.

The differences in the defect predictions between these two simulations would underscore the value and urgency of such a refactoring. We can once again use the RMSE, MAE, and MAPE metrics to measure the difference between the infection rate predicted by the SIS model executed on the simulated refactored SA and on the original SA. For each such hypothetical refactoring, we will pose the following hypotheses:

H₀₄ SIS model produces the same results on the original architecture and with simulated refactoring;

H₁₄ SIS model produces different results on the original architecture and with simulated refactoring.

B. Study Context

We plan to leverage the projects from the Software Quality Dataset (SQuaD) [48] for data collection. The dataset consists of 450 OSS projects, including projects from the Apache Software Foundation, the Mozilla Foundation, and the Linux kernel. SQuaD provides longitudinal commit-level metrics, defect labels derived from established methods, and high-quality process and product metrics, making it appropriate for research on the temporal evolution of software projects and their defects.

C. Data Collection

The data collection consists of identifying suitable projects, reconstructing their architecture across releases, measuring software defects, and simulating the SIS spreading process and the remediation approaches.

1) *Software Architectural Reconstruction*: We will identify projects from the SQuaD dataset [48] written in common programming languages, such as Java. To define an inclusion criterion, we will use the SCC (Sloc Cloc and Code) tool [49] to calculate Lines of Code (LOC) for each project. We will apply the Interquartile Range (IQR) [50] to the LOC distribution and select projects in the top quartile (Q3 to Max) to retain those with sufficient architectural complexity. Among the selected projects, we will rank them based on the number of releases in SQuaD and select the top 5 projects, to have a reasonable number of projects that we can analyze and review deeply. Since we need to reconstruct the project architecture, we will leverage the Understand tool¹ across all available releases. If the reconstruction fails or is not feasible with Understand, we will move to the next available project in our ranking.

2) *Refactor-aware Reconstruction*: Since the components of software are likely to be refactored or new ones introduced, we need to maintain the identity of the components throughout the project history to keep track of the infection status during the defect spreading prediction. For this purpose, we will leverage a refactor-aware static analyzer, such as RefactoringMiner², to identify changes to components throughout development and track modifications, such as renamings.

The SQuaD dataset [48] has the outputs of RefactoringMiner and RefactoringMiner++ in the RMINER and PP_RMINER tables, including the fields *refactoring_type*, *left_filePath*, and *right_filePath* for each release. We will leverage these tables to track component identity changes across releases, including renamings, splits, merges, and other structural refactorings. To validate this tracking step, we will manually sample a subset of release pairs from each project and verify whether the component identity mappings derived from the RMINER data are correct, and report the validation accuracy.

3) *Identifying Software Defects*: The authors of the SQuaD dataset applied many static analysis tools that provided metrics indicating software defects on different levels of granularity, from package to method. We will leverage these metrics to define the diseases we aim to simulate, i.e., convert the metric values into a boolean indicator of whether a given component is infected. We will calculate a global mean μ and standard deviation σ for each metric to convert metric values into boolean labels. If the metric value exceeds $\mu + k\sigma$, the component is labeled as infected. We will determine the value of k based on the distribution of metrics to ensure a proportion of components can be labeled as infected. This

approach ensures that the infection rate $i(t)$ can vary based on different versions, which is essential for SIS model learning.

Since different defect types may have different spreading behaviors, we run the SIS model for each defect type based on metrics available in the SQuaD dataset. The SQuaD dataset provides metrics at the class or file level from different static analysis tools, including complexity metrics such as *class_wmc*, *class_rfc* from CK and *cls_WMC*, *mt_VG* from JASOME, coupling metrics such as *class_cbo*, *class_fanin* from CK, cohesion metrics such as *PercentLackOfCohesion*, *PercentLackOfCohesionModified* from Understand, and rule violations from SonarQube mappable to individual classes. For example, complexity metrics correspond to $RQ_{1.3}$, coupling and cohesion metrics serve as indicators of code smells ($RQ_{1.2}$), and rule violations from SonarQube correspond to technical debt indicators ($RQ_{1.1}$).

We will adopt those metrics that are available on the same level of granularity as the performed architectural reconstruction or on levels below it. For example, if we can reliably reconstruct the studied project at the class level, we could use either class-level metrics or method-level metrics that can be aggregated per class to determine whether a class is infected. We will use the gathered information on component infection status as the ground truth for the models.

4) *Running the SIS Spreading Model*: By leveraging the reconstructed architectural networks of releases, we will simulate the defect spreading process with different parameters of the SIS model. We will note the predicted infection rate and compute the prediction error to learn the pair of SIS parameters that minimizes the prediction error and is thus the best model. Since both of the SIS model parameters, β and γ , correspond to probabilities, we will sample them from the interval $[0; 1]$. We will note specifically the values of the parameters that we can learn from the ground truth data, β_{gt} and γ_{gt} :

The probability of catching the disease, β_{gt} , will be inferred by counting, in each release, all connections between a healthy and an infected component such that the healthy component becomes infected in the following release, and dividing by the total number of connections observed across all releases.

The probability of losing the infection γ_{gt} can be inferred as the inverse of the average length of infection T . If the total of N cases of infection are observed in the ground truth data and components stayed in the infected state for intervals of length t_1, t_2, \dots, t_N , then $T = \frac{\sum t_i}{N}$ and $\gamma_{gt} = \frac{1}{T} = \frac{N}{\sum t_i}$.

We will apply the SIS model by initializing all components as Susceptible, selecting either the ground truth Infected components or an equivalent random set of components at the first release as the seed nodes, then iterating through the releases and their architectural networks and updating the components' Susceptible and Infected status according to the used probabilities (Figure 1), noting the status of each component at each step (release). For each choice of the β and γ parameters, we will run the model a substantial number of times to obtain an average prediction result. For example, Holme [25] analyzed the average of 10^6 repetitions.

¹<https://scitools.com/>

²<https://github.com/tsantalis/RefactoringMiner>

5) *Simulating Remediation Approaches*: To simulate the effect of refactorings on the disease spreading process and defect propagation prediction, we run the best SIS model determined in RQ₁, this time modifying the architectural data to simulate the refactoring. For example, we could simulate a refactoring where the hub components have been removed and each component can have a maximum of, e.g., 10 connections. In this case, we will iterate over the reconstructed architectural networks, and if any component has more than 10 connections, we will randomly select the 10 connections to keep and ignore the rest of the connections. Such an approach will once again require averaging over many repetitions of the process. We will use the same number of repetitions as for RQ₁.

D. Data Analysis

We provide a workflow diagram explaining Data Collection and Analysis procedures to answer the RQs in our Online Appendix³ due to space constraints. To address RQ₁, we evaluate the error of the SIS spreading process in identifying the fraction of infected nodes at each release, the infection rate $i(t)$. For each used model and the ground truth data, we compute standard error metrics, namely MAPE, MAE, and RMSE, to quantify the error of the predicted infection rate (\mathbf{H}_{01} - \mathbf{H}_{11}). We will observe the distributions of the MAE, MAPE, and RMSE error metrics and identify values of β and γ disease parameters that yielded the smallest error according to each metric (\mathbf{H}_{02} - \mathbf{H}_{12}). These values will be used as the SIS spreading parameters for the RQ₂. We will observe if the best parameters for a particular software defect are similar in different projects or not (\mathbf{H}_{03} - \mathbf{H}_{13}).

To address RQ₂, we evaluate the differences in the predicted infection rate $i(t)$ between the model executed on the original architecture, on the simulated refactoring, and the infection rate from the ground truth. For each simulated refactoring, we pair the MAPE, MAE, and RMSE performance metrics from the SIS model run on the original architecture with the same metrics from the SIS model run on the modified architecture to quantify the effect of the refactoring (\mathbf{H}_{04} - \mathbf{H}_{14}). We will analyze all obtained error metrics for RQ₁ and RQ₂ as follows:

We precede all analyses with the **Anderson-Darling (AD) test** to assess normality of residuals (\mathbf{H}_{0AD} : normal; \mathbf{H}_{1AD} : otherwise) [51]. If we reject \mathbf{H}_{0AD} , we will employ the following **nonparametric** tests.

For \mathbf{H}_{01} - \mathbf{H}_{11} and \mathbf{H}_{02} - \mathbf{H}_{12} , we construct, **per project**, an $M \times D$ matrix of mean errors across M SIS parametrizations and D defect types, where each cell averages 1,000 simulation runs. We include the model with parameters $(\beta_{gt}, \gamma_{gt})$, inferred directly from ground-truth infection and recovery rates, as one of the M rows. We apply the **Friedman test** [52] with models as treatments and defect types as blocks. If the Friedman test yields $p < 0.01$, we run **Dunn's post-hoc with Bonferroni correction** to isolate the top-performing model(s) [53]. We reject \mathbf{H}_{01} if any pair of models differs significantly. For \mathbf{H}_{02} , we check whether $(\beta_{gt}, \gamma_{gt})$ belongs to

the same post-hoc group as the best model: if it does, the GT-inferred model is not significantly worse, and we reject \mathbf{H}_{02} in favor of \mathbf{H}_{12} . No separate test is necessary.

For \mathbf{H}_{03} - \mathbf{H}_{13} , we assess parameter consistency across projects in two steps. First, we run a **Friedman test** on a 5×5 matrix (five best models evaluated on all five projects) **for each defect type** to test *performance similarity*: a non-significant result indicates the models are functionally interchangeable. Second, we report the range, coefficient of variation, and bootstrap 99% confidence intervals of the five β^* and five γ^* values to assess *parameter proximity*.

For \mathbf{H}_{04} - \mathbf{H}_{14} , we evaluate R refactoring strategies using an $(R + 1) \times (5 \cdot D)$ matrix (R refactorings plus the original architecture as rows; 5 projects $\times D$ defect types as blocks). We run a **Friedman test** followed by **Dunn's post-hoc with Bonferroni** to determine which refactorings differ significantly from the original architecture.

Normal data. If the AD test fails to reject \mathbf{H}_{0AD} , we replace the Friedman test with **Repeated Measures ANOVA** [54] (to account for the paired structure) and post-hoc comparisons with **Tukey HSD** [55]. Finally, all omnibus tests and the AD test use a family-wise significance level of $\alpha = 0.01$, with the Bonferroni correction maintaining this rate across post-hoc comparisons [56].

IV. THREATS TO VALIDITY

We identify threats to the validity of our study in accordance with the guidelines by Wohlin et al. [47].

Construct Validity. Correctly reconstructing the software architectural networks and identifying software defects are the two crucial steps for the proposed research. We will leverage the SQuAD dataset for the potential projects and software defects. The authors of the dataset compiled the most established and frequently analyzed OSS projects and leveraged several widely accepted and adopted static analysis tools to identify software defects. For software architecture reconstruction, we will leverage and rely on the output of established static analysis tools, such as Understand, as frequently done in Software Architecture research [43].

What is more, analysing the refactorings and changes in the components to track the same components across the release history might prove inaccurate. Thus, if we cannot match the same component in two consecutive releases, the SIS model will be ineffective, since if a component gets infected, we will not be able to pass the infection status to the same component in the next release. Such challenges have been observed when modeling software architectures as temporal networks, and are a natural limitation of such data [22].

Internal Validity. The leveraged SIS disease spreading model might not be the most suitable model for predicting defect propagation in software. The only thing that we can measure as the output of this model is the infection rate of the network in each snapshot, which does not tell us much about the individual components being infected. The most common model used in other applications of Network Science is Susceptible-Infected-Recovered, where at the end of the

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20609618>

simulation all nodes are either Susceptible or Recovered. The ratio of these two types of nodes is used as another metric for network health. In our application, we cannot leverage that model, since we may never assume a component is fully recovered from a defect and not susceptible to it anymore. Moreover, most works on temporal networks that leverage disease spreading models actually loop through the available networks several times to ensure that the simulation is long enough and that long-term effects are apparent. This is done under the assumption that the studied data is periodic, e.g., human activity in a 24-h cycle. However, such an assumption cannot hold for a sequence of architectural networks. Thus, we will only run the simulation going through the reconstructed networks once. This might affect the outcome or hide the long-term effects, depending on the available release history.

External Validity. We assume that a defect could spread from one component to another only if they are connected within the software architectural network, i.e., one of the components depends on another. However, attention is increasingly drawn to coupling introduced by the developer activity outside the boundaries of software architecture, namely, the organizational coupling [57], [58], [59]. Developers could commit to several components simultaneously [60], or frequently switch between components that they work on [57]. If a certain developer is prone to introducing a specific defect, i.e., overly complex code, this defect might spread among the components they work on, despite the components not depending on each other [58], [59]. Thus, to properly model defect spreading, it might be necessary to augment the architectural network obtained with static analysis with the information on components coupled due to developer activity [61].

Conclusion Validity. As the current work is only the proposal of the methodology, we cannot anticipate our conclusions at this point.

V. CONCLUSION

Our registered report outlines the methodology of an empirical investigation of modeling and predicting defect propagation in SA with the disease spreading models from Network Science, namely the SIS spreading model. The results of this empirical study will yield the following insights and contributions: (i) which software defects can be modeled as a SIS spreading process and how to appropriately learn the model parameters; (ii) which refactorings can be simulated with the defect prediction model to observe their effect on defect spreading.

To researchers, our study will provide the possibility to leverage existing and mature methodology from Network Science to study and predict defect propagation in software with SIS spreading models. For practitioners, our findings will provide ways to prioritize remediation of different defects and analyze the effects of potential architectural refactorings.

Future works stemming from the successful implementation of the planned study could include:

- Evaluation of more complex disease spreading models for defect prediction;

- Modeling the spreading of more kinds of defects;
- Comparing the spreading of defects in different programming languages or in more complex, polyglot systems across the different languages (microservices);
- Modeling the effect of developer-induced coupling between components not connected architecturally on disease spreading.

Furthermore, a negative result of our study would also yield important observations. If we fail to model and predict defects via disease spreading models, this would indicate that defects do not spread through the project’s source code. Thus, different theories and models for analyzing defect propagation should be developed based on different principles.

DECLARATION ON THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI

The authors used ChatGPT for suggestions on improving textual clarity. All research design, data analysis, interpretations, and manuscripts were created by the authors themselves.

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